

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

Annual Report 2011–2012

DIRECTORS, JULY 1, 2011–JUNE 30, 2012

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THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES (CLIR) is an independent, nonprofit organization that forges strategies to enhance research, teaching, and learning environments in collaboration with libraries, cultural institutions, and communities of higher learning. CLIR aspires to transform the information landscape to support the advancement of knowledge.

CLIR promotes forward-looking collaborative solutions that transcend disciplinary, institutional, professional, and geographic boundaries in support of the public good. In pursuing its mission, CLIR is committed to building trust, retaining independence, fostering collaboration, cultivating effective leadership, and capitalizing on strategic opportunities.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2011-2012

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The following institutions and individuals provide crucial support for the activities and programs of the Council on Library and Information Resources (as of June 30, 2012):

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(AS OF JUNE 30, 2012)

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LETTER FROM THE PRESIDENT AND CHAIRMAN

Charles Henry
President

Stephen Nichols
Chairman of the Board

The Return on Investment

Reflecting on the past year, we can see clearly that CLIR is continuing to build vigorously upon its mission: forging strategies to enhance research, teaching, and learning environments. In doing so, CLIR has formed collaborative partnerships with libraries, cultural institutions, and associations of higher learning to train an emerging profession in service to advanced research (postdoctoral fellows in data curation), to create a registry that ties together scores of institutions and hundreds of valuable rare and special collections that otherwise would remain out of sight and inaccessible (hidden collections), and to mentor a growing cohort of future leaders (through the Frye Leadership Institute, now the Leading Change Institute).

As an organization that relies on its sponsors for financial support, we are always aware of the issue of “return on investment.” What do our hundreds of sponsors receive from CLIR that is especially valuable, unique, and integral to their advancement? CLIR’s research reports and array of communication types (e.g., routine publications, blogs, colloquiums, online connections, and posting spaces) are among the most respected and cited of their kind. The reincorporation of the Digital Library Federation has stimulated a cadre of technical experts to work more closely together on a variety of projects and issues. CLIR also lends its talented staff to important projects on behalf of our sponsors, such as the Digital Public Library of America and the Digital Preservation Network, particularly when those projects hold considerable promise for our successful evolution in a digital era.

In addition, CLIR raises grant funds that are redirected to our sponsors and partnering communities. Over the last seven years, CLIR has allocated \$70,000 for our Zipf fellows; \$2,000,000 for dissertation fellowships; \$1,500,000 for the Early English Book Project; more than \$800,000 for postdoctoral fellowships; \$158,000 for participatory design workshops; approximately \$626,000 for the Communities of Knowledge project; and more than \$10,000,000 in grants for our Hidden Collections program. This Council believes strongly in reinvesting assets to enhance our sponsors’ ability to innovate, to help make their resources available to a wider public, and to foster new discovery.

During this past year, CLIR has initiated a variety of new projects designed and managed by our staff. They have focused on topics of immense complexity and urgency, with potentially transformative results. The expansion of our postdoctoral fellows program into data curation is one of these. Anvil Academic Publishing is another. Anvil is a partnership of universities and colleges that will guide the migration from printed books and journals to fully digital objects of expression. These new forms of scholarship—which are often richly layered works that can include not only the product of the research, but also extensive data (e.g., text, image, sound), algorithms, visualization tools, and linkages to other relevant research—will not “fit” into a printed page. Anvil will explore ways to capture and sustain the complex environment in which these discoveries are made and promulgated. Anvil’s business model is also indicative of CLIR’s mission. Relatively modest subscriptions from collaborating institutions are pooled with significant grant money to leverage their contributions. Whereas even large institutions cannot afford the hundreds of thousands of dollars needed to migrate to a digital publishing platform, Anvil and its partners can accomplish that migration in an efficient and cost effective way with a smaller investment from each.

Finally, much of this year has been devoted to developing CLIR’s Committee on Coherence at Scale. The committee, composed of presidents, provosts, and leaders in library and technology spheres, will work to correlate and bring coherence to the many very large-scale digital projects in the United States. Its goals are ambitious: to develop methods, guidelines, and recommendations that would allow academic leaders to instantiate sustainable communities of practice that would in concert produce a new, more logical, and more rational system of higher education. The committee can assist in reconceptualizing the traditional model of competing, stand-alone institutions into a coherent system of higher education that preserves the identity and independence of universities and colleges, but brings together many of the functions and support services that undergird scholarship and teaching. Such a system would contribute to a well-wrought and sustainable communal good.

Working at the nexus of higher education administration, librarianship, information technology, and scholarly communication, CLIR is uniquely positioned to accomplish these tasks. And, as always, this work will be conducted explicitly on your behalf.

Charles Henry
President

Stephen Nichols
Chairman

THE PROGRAMS

July 1, 2011–June 30, 2012

DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Objective: Define the base technologies of computation and communication, the software programs, and the data curation and preservation programs that are national in scale and necessary to manage very large-scale multimedia data sets, especially those pertaining to the digital record of our cultural heritage.

Digital Library Federation Program

The Digital Library Federation (DLF) program focuses on the technological aspects of developing, sustaining, and aggregating digital resources; promoting standards, protocols, and best practices; and supporting digital architectures that are open source, extensible, and interoperable. The DLF is integral to CLIR's activities in data curation and linked data, and it has taken a lead role in the Content & Scope Workstream for the Digital Public Library of America.

The DLF Forum continues to serve as an important venue for the exchange of information that will lead to a better understanding of the elements and complexity of digital library evolution, as well as for collaboration on practical work. The 2011 Fall Forum was held October 31–November 1 in Baltimore, Maryland.

In April 2012, CLIR's Board appointed a six-member DLF Advisory Committee, comprising three Board members and three members of the DLF community. The committee will advise the DLF director on matters relating to program activities, initiatives, partnerships, and strategy.

Development of Data Curation Skills

CLIR's recent report, *The Problem of Data*, points out the urgent need for a reliable and increasingly sophisticated professional cohort to support data-intensive research in our colleges, universities, and research centers. The report includes findings from two studies commissioned in the fall of 2011. The first study, conducted by Lori Jahnke and Andrew Asher, examines data curation practices among scholars at five institutions of higher education. The second study, by Spencer D. C. Keralis, is an environmental

scan of professional development needs and of education and training opportunities for digital curation in the academy.

In an effort to raise awareness and build capacity for sound data management practices throughout the academy, CLIR launched the CLIR/DLF Data Curation Fellowship Program in the spring of 2012 with support from the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. The program provides recent Ph.D.s with professional development, education, and training opportunities in data curation for the sciences and social sciences. In the Fellowship's pilot cycle (2012–2014), CLIR is cohosting six fellows with its partner institutions: Indiana University, Lehigh University, McMaster University, Purdue University, the University of California Los Angeles, and the University of Michigan.

With generous support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR will expand the program in 2013 to include new Data Curation Fellowships in Medieval Studies.

ARL/DLF E-Science Institute

In July 2011, CLIR's DLF Program and the Association for Research Libraries (ARL) launched the ARL/DLF E-Science Institute. The institute was created to give participants the tools and the knowledge needed to develop a sound strategic approach to exploring and supporting e-science within their organizations. Its program comprises a set of interactive modules that take small teams of individuals from academic institutions through a dynamic learning process to strengthen and advance their capacity to support computational scientific research. Sixty-seven institutions and 180 people participated in the E-Science Institute, which culminated in three capstone events in late 2011 and early 2012.

In June 2012, CLIR announced that the institute would continue for the 2012–2013 year as the ARL/DLF/DuraSpace E-Science Institute.

Assessment of the Digging into Data Challenge

In January 2010, CLIR entered a cooperative agreement with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) Office of Digital Humanities to provide a strategic assessment of the Digging into Data Challenge, an international grant program first funded by NEH, the United Kingdom's Joint Information Systems Committee, the U.S. National Science Foundation, and Canada's Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council. The Challenge was launched to better understand how "big data" changes the research landscape for the humanities and social sciences. Scholars in these disciplines now use massive databases of materials that range from digitized books, newspapers, and music to transactional data such as web searches, sensor data, or cell phone records. The Challenge seeks

to discover what new, computationally based research methods might be applied to these sources.

In its first year, the Digging into Data Challenge made awards to eight teams of scholars, librarians, and computer and information scientists. Over the following two years, CLIR staff members Christa Williford and Charles Henry conducted site visits, interviews, and focus groups to understand how these complex international projects were being managed, what challenges they faced, and what project teams were learning from the experience.

In June 2012, their findings were published in the report, *One Culture. Computationally Intensive Research in the Humanities and Social Sciences*. The report also included a series of recommendations for researchers, administrators, scholarly societies, academic publishers, research libraries, and funding agencies.

Digital Public Library of America

The Digital Public Library of America (DPLA) is envisioned as a large-scale digital library that will “make the cultural and scientific heritage of humanity available, free of charge, to all.” Planning for the DPLA began late in 2010. The Berkman Center for Internet & Society at Harvard University serves as the secretariat. The DPLA is currently organized by six workstreams that are defined and coordinated through a steering committee. The workstreams include Audience & Participation; Financial/Business Models; Governance; Legal Issues; Technical Aspects; and Content & Scope, which is led by DLF Program Director Rachel Frick.

In October 2011, the DPLA Plenary Meeting brought together diverse stakeholders in an open forum to present the vision for the DPLA effort and to share models, prototypes, tools, and interfaces that demonstrated how the DPLA might index and provide access to a wide range of broadly distributed content. Among the submissions was a prototype from CLIR’s DLF Program and the Center for Informatics Research in Science and Scholarship (CIRSS) at the Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of Illinois. The prototype leveraged the Institute of Museum and Library Services’ Digital Collections and Content (IMLS DCC) resource and DLF Aquifer content as a core collection for the DPLA. Launched in 2003, the IMLS DCC is an aggregation of digital collections from libraries, museums, and archives, supported by the IMLS and developed through a collaboration between the CIRSS and the University of Illinois Library.

As part of the project to develop the prototype, CLIR commissioned a comparative report that reviews the research on the management of

large-scale collections and practical efforts to aggregate them. The report, *Core Infrastructure Considerations for Large Digital Libraries*, by Geneva Henry, was published in July 2012. The study examines basic functional aspects of large digital libraries and draws on examples of existing digital libraries to illustrate their varying approaches to storage and content delivery, metadata approaches and harvesting, search and discovery, services and applications, and system sustainability.

The staff of the Content & Scope Workstream held a meeting in February 2012 that focused on discussing and formulating phase one of the DPLA Collection Development Strategic Plan: metadata aggregation of open cultural heritage objects. A DPLA Think Tank meeting was held June 15, 2012 to discuss technical architecture plans in the context of expected DPLA content.

SCHOLARSHIP AND RESEARCH

Objective: Explore and assess new research methodologies, emerging fields of inquiry, intellectual strategies involving data gathering and collaboration, and modes of communication, including sharing of research data and publishing models, that are likely to define the next generation of scholars.

Anvil Academic Publishing

In February 2012, CLIR and the National Institute for Technology in Liberal Education (NITLE) joined forces with a group of colleges and universities to establish Anvil Academic, a digital publisher for the humanities. Anvil Academic focuses on publishing new forms of scholarship that cannot be adequately conveyed in the traditional monograph and serves as a testbed for alternate business models for scholarly publishing.

Together, NITLE and CLIR are developing the production system for use by other institutions, each of which will have the opportunity to publish under its own imprint. It is expected that Anvil Academic will publish its first title in early 2013. NITLE and CLIR will enlist additional publishers, scholarly societies, librarians, administrators, and faculty to participate in planning and developing Anvil-forged college and university publishing enterprises.

Fred Moody serves as editor of Anvil Academic. In June 2012, Lisa Spiro, coordinator of NITLE's Innovation Studio and director of NITLE Labs, was named program manager. That same month, Korey Jackson, American Council of Learned Societies Public Fellow and former CLIR Postdoctoral Fellow, was named program coordinator and analyst.

Anvil Academic Publishing received startup funding from the Brown

2011–2012 Postdoctoral Fellows in Academic Libraries

Jessica Aberle, Lehigh University
Katherine Akers, Emory University
Peter Broadwell, UCLA
Jason Brodeur, McMaster University
Brock Dubbels, McMaster University
Arthur (Mitch) Fraas, University of Pennsylvania
Matthew J. Lavin, University of Nebraska-Lincoln
John Maclachlan, McMaster University
Ekaterina Neklyudova, McMaster University
Jennifer Parrott, Bucknell University
Jennifer Redmond, Bryn Mawr College
Christopher Teeter, McMaster University
Yi Shen, Johns Hopkins University

Foundation, Inc. In addition, Stanford University, the University of Virginia, Washington University in St. Louis, Bryn Mawr College, Amherst College, Middlebury College, and Southwestern University provide funds and staffing. Anvil Academic is working closely with innovative programs developed by the University of Michigan, especially MPublishing, and drawing on Johns Hopkins University's exemplary experience with digital humanities project development.

Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries Program

CLIR Postdoctoral Library Fellows work on projects that forge, renovate, and strengthen connections between academic library collections and their users. The program offers scholars who have recently earned their Ph.D.s a chance to work in academic libraries on projects that are related to their disciplines and, thus, benefit both the scholar and the library. The fellows have the opportunity to develop research models, collaborate with information specialists, and explore new career opportunities. Participating libraries benefit from the expertise of accomplished scholars who can invigorate approaches to collection use and teaching, contribute field-specific knowledge, and provide insight into the future of scholarship. In the 2011–2012 academic year, the program had 13 current and continuing fellows. As of May 2012, the project had supported 64 fellows, and 26 institutions had participated as hosts.

Workshops on Participatory Design in Academic Libraries

Led by Nancy Fried Foster, director of anthropological research at the University of Rochester's River Campus Libraries, the workshops on participatory design in academic libraries provide attendees with an overview of the participatory design process and strategies for including faculty members, graduate students, undergraduates, and library staff. The workshops feature extensive interaction among participants, as well as between participants and research subjects. The first workshop was held in 2007, and as of June 30, 2012, more than 270 people had participated.

In May 2012, the first CLIR "Seminar on Issues of Participatory Design in Academic Libraries" was held at the University of Maryland in College Park. The seminar was an opportunity for previous participants of CLIR participatory design workshops to present projects that they have conducted using the techniques they learned from Nancy Foster.

Teams from 12 sponsoring institutions gave presentations on such topics as ways to collaborate with undergraduates in an anthropology course on a library space/use study, gathering information about student use of a library renovation, the transition of undergraduates from high school to college, the process and challenges of data analysis, and the importance of failure in learning how to conduct participatory design projects. Foster

2011 Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Awards

American Geographical Society Library, University of Milwaukee
Providing Access to the Archives of the American Geographical Society, \$259,900

Amistad Research Center
Increasing Access to Africana Collections: The American Committee on Africa and The Africa Fund Records, \$238,200

Brown University Library
The Gordon Hall and Grace Hoag Collection of Dissenting and Extremist Printed Propaganda, Part II, \$376,100

Center for Jewish History
Illuminating Hidden Collections at the Center for Jewish History, \$229,600

Dance Heritage Coalition
Foundations of Dance Research (Foundations), \$350,000

Fray Angélico Chávez History Library
Mapas históricos de Nuevo México = Historic New Mexico Maps, \$179,600

Georgetown University, Lauinger Library
Undiscovered Printmakers: Hidden Treasures in Georgetown University's Library, \$95,200

History San Jose
Documenting Technology Innovation: Perham Collection of Early Electronics, \$86,600

Maine Maritime Museum
Merchant Mariners Muster: Cataloging Crew Manuscripts, \$125,600

Mennonite Heritage Center
The Pennsylvania German Textiles of the Goshenhoppen Historians, the Mennonite Heritage Center and the Schwenkfelder Library & Heritage Center, \$98,500

Museum of Vertebrate Zoology
Cataloging Hidden Archives of the Museum of Vertebrate Zoology: Increasing Integration and Accessibility for Interdisciplinary Research, \$481,800

The New York Archival Society
Cataloging Artifacts and Related Records of the World Trade Center Attack on September 11, 2001, \$120,000

New-York Historical Society
The New-York Historical Society American Almanac Collection, \$255,700

North Carolina State University Libraries
Acting for Animals: Revealing the Records of Animal Rights and Animal Welfare Movements, \$219,600

Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey
Cataloging Women in Jazz Collections at the Institute of Jazz Studies, \$165,000

San Diego Museum of Man
Capturing History: Cataloging the San Diego Museum of Man's Photographic Collection, \$115,200

Smithsonian Institution, Archives of American Art
Uncovering Hidden Audio Visual Media Documenting Post-Modern Art at the Archives of American Art, \$222,700

Texas A&M University, Cushing Memorial Library & Archives
Discovering a New World: Cataloging Old and Rare Imprints from Colonial and Early Independent Mexico, \$84,500

University of California, Santa Barbara, University Art Museum
Cataloguing Southern California's Architectural History, \$183,500

More detail on this year's funded projects can be found at <http://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/awards/index.html/#2011>.

presented new information-gathering and analytical methods, and she facilitated a group discussion on how to gain support for participatory design projects. A report on the seminar is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub155>. A second seminar is planned for June 2013.

An Ethnographic Research User Group was formed shortly after the seminar. Composed of alumni from the participatory design workshops and other interested constituents, it is a resource for librarians and academic technologists in higher education who aspire to build community, collaborate, network, and share information. The group advances its mission by organizing regular online meetings and meeting informally at events where multiple members are in one place.

Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives: Building a New Research Environment

CLIR's Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Program supports efforts to expose unknown or underutilized cultural materials to communities of scholars, students, and other users who need them for their work. Nineteen projects were selected to receive a total of \$4 million in awards for the 2011 funding cycle.

Since 2008 when the program was initiated, 65 projects, representing a wide range of institutions across the United States, have been funded. The projects have already made impressively large volumes of cultural materials in diverse formats accessible to scholars. In late June 2012, CLIR launched its Registry of Hidden Special Collections and Archives, a web-based browsable registry of hidden materials compiled from data submitted by grant applicants.

Work continues on a multiyear study to describe successful strategies for engaging users with collections. The study, titled "Observations on Scholarly Engagement with Hidden Special Collections and Archives," is being undertaken by a team of former participants in CLIR's Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries Program. The study team is focusing on three subject areas that are well represented among funded projects: civil rights, natural history, and literature. In March 2012, team members Michelle Morton (Cañada College) and Kelly Miller (University of California Los Angeles) hosted a multiproject online meeting for archivists working with civil rights collections and prepared a short essay about the experiences of students who have been working with these collections; the essay will appear in the forthcoming issue of *ArchiveJournal*. Tim Stinson (North Carolina State University) spoke on behalf of the team at the June 2012 meeting of the Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections. The team plans to present findings related to the impact of hidden collections cataloging and related programming on students and scholars in additional venues in the coming year.

2011–2012 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Elise Bonner, Princeton University
Adam Boss, Brown University
William Brown, Johns Hopkins University
Rebecca Herman, University of California, Berkeley
Thomas Hooker, Harvard University
Jang Wook Huh, Columbia University
Neelima Jeychandran, University of California,
 Los Angeles
Seth LeJacq, The Johns Hopkins University
Kara Moskowitz, Emory University
Sylvia Mullins, Georgetown University
Elizabeth Nelson, Indiana University
Kimberly Powers, University of Michigan
Matthew Rarey, University of Wisconsin, Madison
Frederick Schenker, University of Wisconsin,
 Madison
Rafal Stepien, Columbia University
Mirela Tanta, University of Illinois at Chicago
Zita Worley, University of California, Riverside

The Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Program is supported by funding from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation.

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships

The Mellon Dissertation Fellowship Program helps junior scholars in the humanities and related social science fields gain skill and creativity in developing knowledge from original sources; enables dissertation writers to do research wherever relevant sources may be, rather than just where financial support is available; encourages more extensive and innovative uses of original sources in libraries, archives, museums, historical societies, and related repositories in the United States and abroad; and provides insight from the viewpoint of doctoral candidates into the effective development of scholarly resources for access in the future.

The fellowship program, initiated in 2002, has supported 143 graduate students as they carried out their dissertation research in a variety of public and private libraries and archives.

PRESERVATION AND ACCESS

Objective: Examine sustainable strategies for preserving all media, analog and traditional, and heighten public awareness of the risks of failing to plan for preservation.

Preserving Recorded Sound Heritage

Since 2004, CLIR has conducted work under contract with the Library of Congress and the National Recording Preservation Board in support of an ongoing study of the state of recorded sound preservation and restoration. In 2011–2012, CLIR also assisted in production of a forthcoming survey of American silent feature films.

CLIR/Library of Congress Fellowship

In spring 2011, CLIR established the CLIR/Library of Congress Fellowship, which supports original-source dissertation research in the humanities or related social sciences in the Preservation Research and Testing Division of the Preservation Directorate at the Library. The fellowship is offered as part of the Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Sources. Stephanie Stillo, of the University of Kansas, was awarded the fellowship for 2012 for research on “Seville and the Cartographic Origins of the Early Modern Hispanic World.”

LEADERSHIP EDUCATION AND CULTIVATION

Objective: Investigate and seek to define the skills and expertise needed to administer, inspire, and inform the next generation.

Leadership through New Communities of Knowledge

Launched in July 2009 as a partnership between CLIR and the Council of Independent Colleges (CIC), the Leadership through New Communities of Knowledge Program offers professional development opportunities for library staff at small-to-midsized private colleges and universities. Since the program's inception, CLIR has sent participants from CIC schools to numerous workshops on data curation, work restructuring, archival practice, undergraduate research behavior, and information fluency.

CLIR collaborated with the CIC to hold a symposium on the Future of the Liberal Arts College Library on October 10–12, 2011, at Alverno College in Milwaukee, Wisconsin. The symposium focused on the ways in which the evolving missions of private liberal arts colleges influence the ways in which their libraries plan and operate. Many of these colleges have added preprofessional, distance education, and adult education programs to the traditional liberal arts curriculum, but their library collections and services do not always evolve in tandem. This symposium offered staff from small-to-midsized colleges and universities the chance to draw upon each other's expertise for effecting change at the intersection of libraries and liberal arts colleges. Victor E. Ferrall, Jr., author of *Liberal Arts on the Brink*, gave the symposium's opening keynote. Jessamyn West, author of *Without a Net: Librarians Bridging the Digital Divide*, presented the closing keynote.

The project, supported with funds from the IMLS, was originally slated to run through June 2012 but has been extended through June 2013. It will focus primarily on organizing online webinars and training sessions, and supporting attendance at conferences.

Frye Leadership Institute

The Frye Leadership Institute, cosponsored by CLIR, EDUCAUSE, and Emory University, was created to prepare and develop the next generation of leaders in libraries, information services, and higher education. The institute welcomed its first class of students in 1999, and institutes were held annually thereafter until 2009. In 2010, the Frye Leadership Institute took a one-year hiatus to develop and articulate a new program that addresses higher education's leadership needs in an era of unprecedented change. The new curriculum, implemented at the 2011 institute, engages individuals who are already leaders in their profession and seeks to further develop their skills, particularly in the area of advocacy.

Frye Leadership Institute Participants 2012

Cynthia Abercrombie, Harvey Mudd College
Anthony Adade, Elizabeth City State University
Randall Alberts, Ringling College of Art and Design
Kevin Ashford-Rowe, Griffith University
Dale Askey, McMaster University
Ronald Bergmann, Lehman College/City University of New York
Angela Blackstone, University of California, Berkeley
Mary Ann Blair, Carnegie Mellon University
Ellysa Cahoy, Penn State University Libraries
Josh Callahan, Humboldt State University
Michael Cato, University of North Carolina, Charlotte
Huapei Chen, University of Texas, Austin
Kirstin Dougan, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
Deane Eastwood, Harvard University
Bradford Eden, Valparaiso University
Steve Fabiani, Haverford College
William Frady, Western Carolina University
Anthony Helm, Dartmouth College
Carol Hixson, University of South Florida St. Petersburg
Nancy Hoover, Marylhurst University
Corrie Hutchinson, Stephens College
John Jeries, St. Catherine University
Michael Kubit, Case Western Reserve University
Jonathan Leamon, Williams College
Tim Lockridge, University of Southern Indiana
Frank Mathew, University of Mississippi
Keith McIntosh, Pima County Community College District
Cindy Mitchell, University of Maine System
Lisa Moeckel, Syracuse University Library
Raymond Nardelli, Colgate University
Christine Nugent, Warren Wilson College
Jessica Olin, Hiram College
Jim Phillips, University of California, Santa Cruz
Terry Reese, Oregon State University
Leslie Reynolds, Texas A&M University
Jose Rodriguez, Emory University
Gina Siesing, Tufts University
Jennifer Sparrow, Virginia Tech
Richard Trentham, Rhodes College
Katie Vale, Harvard University
Keith Weber, College of Mount St. Joseph

The 2012 Frye Leadership Institute, held June 3–8 in Washington, D.C., was attended by 41 participants from a wide variety of colleges and universities. Institute co-deans were Elliott Shore, chief information officer at Bryn Mawr College and CLIR Presidential Fellow; and Joanne Kossuth, vice president for operations and chief information officer at EDUCAUSE.

Chief Information Officers Group

CLIR's Chief Information Officers Group is composed of 33 directors of organizations that have merged their library and technology units on liberal arts college campuses. The group met in October 2011 and April 2012 to discuss common concerns and to exchange ideas about possible solutions for organizational and policy problems on their campuses. They explored such topics as open access; the effect of the recession on their organizational structure, technology, business strategies, and attitudes; cloud computing; portals versus Web 2.0; strategies for measuring the use and effectiveness of services; and ideas for prioritizing services. Throughout the year, members exchange ideas and solutions through a listserv.

Rick Peterson Fellowship

Joshua Honn, digital scholarship library fellow at Northwestern University Library's Center for Scholarly Communication and Digital Curation, was awarded the 2012 Rick Peterson Fellowship. CLIR and NITLE established the fellowship in 2011 in honor of Richard (Rick) Allen Peterson, a leader in information technology and academic computing. The fellowship is awarded annually to an early career information technology professional or librarian who has reached beyond traditional boundaries to resolve a significant challenge facing digital libraries. The fellowship supports participation in the annual NITLE Symposium and in CLIR's DLF Forum.

Zipf Fellowship

Jodi Schneider, a Ph.D. candidate in the Digital Enterprise Research Institute at the National University of Ireland in Galway, was selected to receive the A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management for 2012. Her research focuses on information management and knowledge representation of contested information from social media.

For the past 16 years, CLIR has awarded the annual Zipf Fellowship to a graduate student in a field of information management or systems who best exemplifies the ideals of A. R. Zipf, the information science pioneer for whom the award is named.

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Molly Schwartz, a library science student at the University of Maryland at College Park, was awarded the 2012 Rovelstad Scholarship in

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group Members (as of 6/30/12)

Param Bedi, Bucknell University
Frank Cervone, Perdue University Calumet
Jim Cubit, Lake Forest College
Greg Diment, Kalamazoo College
Charling Chang Fagan, Sarah Lawrence College
Chris Ferguson, Pacific Lutheran University
Megan Fitch, Beloit College
Chip German, Millersville College
Ronald Griggs, Kenyon College
Lee Hisle, Connecticut College
Rick Holmgren, Allegheny College
Robert Johnson, Rhodes College
Todd Kelley, Carthage College
Kenneth Kochien, Colby-Sawyer College
Paul Mattson, Luther College
Neil McElroy, Lafayette College
Pam McQuesten, Occidental College
Michael Miller, California Polytechnic State University
Kathy Monday, University of Richmond
Pattie Orr, Baylor University
Charlotte Slocum Patriquin, Mount Holyoke College
Rick Provine, DePauw University
Ravi Ravishanker, Wellesley College
Robert Renaud, Dickinson College
Suzanne Risley, Mitchell College
Mike Roy, Middlebury College
Vicki Sells, Sewanee: The University of the South
Elliott Shore, Bryn Mawr College
Carol Smith, DePauw University
Bruce Taggart, Lehigh University
John Unsworth, Brandeis University
Gene Wiemers, Bates College
Frank Wojcik, The College at Brockport, State
 University of New York

International Librarianship. Schwartz is creating her own specialization in international archives by combining courses in archives, international librarianship, and e-government.

Instituted in 2002, the Rovelstad Scholarship encourages library students who have an interest in international library work by enabling them to attend the World Library and Information Congress, the annual meeting of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions.

COMMUNICATIONS AND PUBLICATIONS

In February 2012, CLIR launched a new website at www.clir.org. In addition to the full range of publications, news, and award information featured on its previous website, new functionality was included for CLIR sponsors and DLF members. The most important of these is CLIR Connect, an area where sponsors and members can sign in to initiate or join discussions, post resources, connect with other members of the sponsor community, share blogs, and more.

In June 2012, CLIR launched a weekly blog series, titled “Re: Thinking.”

Between July 1, 2011 and June 30, 2012, CLIR issued the following publications:

- *“Rome Wasn’t Digitized in a Day”: Building a Cyberinfrastructure for Digital Classicists*, by Alison Babeu. August 2011.
- *Linked Data for Libraries, Museums, and Archives: Survey and Workshop Report*. October 2011.
- *CLIR Annual Report 2010–2011*. November 2011.
- *One Culture. Computationally Intensive Research in the Humanities and Social Sciences*, by Christa Williford and Charles Henry. June 2012.
- “Supporting Humanities Doctoral Student Success: A Collaborative Project between Cornell University Library and Columbia University Libraries,” by Gabriela Castro Gessner, Damon E. Jaggars, Jennifer Rutner, and Kornelia Tancheva. *Ruminations*, October 2011.
- *CLIR Issues*, numbers 82–87.

ADVISORY GROUPS AS OF JUNE 30, 2012

Academic Librarians Advisory Committee

Tyrone Cannon
University of San Francisco

Charles Henry
CLIR

Robert Renaud
Dickinson College

Connie Vinita Dowell
Vanderbilt University

Michael D. Miller
California Polytechnic University

Joanne Schneider
Colgate University

A. R. Zipf Fellowship Selection Committee

Christine Borgman
University of California, Los Angeles

Deanna B. Marcum
Library of Congress

Rena Zipf

Digital Library Federation Program Advisory Committee

Stephen Rhind-Tutt
Alexander Street Press

Sarah Shreeves
IDEALS and Scholarly Commons

Winston Tabb
Johns Hopkins University

David Rumsey
David Rumsey Map Collection and
Cartography Associates

Tito Sierra
Massachusetts Institute for Technology

Jennifer Vinopal
New York University

Hidden Collections Review Panel, 2011 Final Proposal Round

Rachel Frick
CLIR

Geneva Henry
Rice University

Stephen G. Nichols
Johns Hopkins University

Joan Giesecke
University of Nebraska at Lincoln

Mary Kelley
University of Michigan

Elliott Shore
Bryn Mawr College

Jacqueline Goldsby
Yale University

Ronald L. Larsen
University of Pittsburgh

Richard V. Szary
University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Charles Henry
CLIR

Jerome McGann
University of Virginia

Hidden Collections Review Panel, 2012 Initial Proposal Phase

Rachel Frick
CLIR

Jerome McGann
University of Virginia

Lisa Spiro
National Institute for Technology in
Liberal Education

Jacqueline Goldsby
Yale University

Dennis Meissner
Minnesota Historical Society

Richard V. Szary
University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Charles Henry
CLIR

Stephen G. Nichols
Johns Hopkins University

Ronald L. Larsen
University of Pittsburgh

Lynn Ransom
The University of Pennsylvania Libraries

Mellon Fellowships Selection Committee 2012

Kevin Bartig
Michigan State University

Mark Dimunation
Library of Congress

Lindsay Weiss
Stanford University

José O. Díaz
Ohio State University

Roy Domenico
St. Thomas Hall

Susie Woo
University of Southern California

Charles Henry
CLIR

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE IN THE PERIOD JULY 1, 2011 TO JUNE 30, 2012

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
American Museum of Natural History New York, NY	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "For the People, for Education, for Science: Web Access to the American Museum of Natural History Archives"	12/16/2010	\$117,600
Amistad Research Center New Orleans, LA	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Increasing Access to Africana Collections: The American Committee on Africa and The Africa Fund Records"	12/9/2011	\$238,200
Amistad Research Center New Orleans, LA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Working for Freedom: Documenting Civil Rights Organization"	1/23/2009	\$250,000
Arizona State University Libraries Tempe, AZ	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project "Labor Rights are Civil Rights"	12/16/2010	\$155,600
David Bertagni Bryn Mawr, PA	To conduct a review and analysis of CLIR's IT configuration	9/23/2011	\$3,000
Brooklyn Historical Society Brooklyn, NY	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering the Secrets of Brooklyn's 19th Century Past: Creation to Consolidation"	11/13/2009	\$440,491
Brown University Providence, RI	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The Gordon Hall and Grace Hoag Collection of Dissenting and Extremist Printed Propaganda, Part II"	12/9/2011	\$376,100
California Digital Library Oakland, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering California's Environmental Collections: A Collaborative Approach"	11/13/2009	\$446,817
Eric Celeste St. Paul, MN	To provide technical assistance with the DLF website	12/3/2010	\$9,200
Center for the History of Medicine, Countway Library, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Foundations of Public Health Policy"	12/1/2008	\$217,933
Center for Jewish History New York, NY	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Illuminating Hidden Collections at the Center for Jewish History"	12/9/2011	\$229,600
Lauren Coats Baton Rouge, LA	To coordinate CLIR's monthly Postdoctoral Synchronous Sessions	10/25/2010	\$2,600
Lauren Coats Baton Rouge, LA	To coordinate CLIR's monthly postdoctoral fellows synchronous sessions.	10/31/2011	\$900

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
College of Charleston Charleston, SC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the cataloguing of the library's Jewish Heritage Collection	12/4/2009	\$184,000
David Consiglio Bryn Mawr, PA	To develop and administer four surveys in support of the IMLS funded "New Communities of Knowledge" grant	10/24/2011	\$7,500
Cornell University Ithaca, NY	To conduct a joint user needs study of graduate students in the humanities at Cornell and Columbia Universities	1/18/2010	\$15,000
Dance Heritage Coalition Washington, DC	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Foundations of Dance Research"	12/9/2011	\$350,000
Emory University Atlanta, GA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Archives from Atlanta, Cradle of the Civil Rights Movement: the papers of Andrew Young, SCLC, and NAACP-Atlanta, GA"	1/23/2009	\$399,172
Nancy Foster Rochester, NY	To conduct up to three workshops on Participatory Design in Academic Libraries between May 1, 2012 and December 31, 2012	3/19/2012	\$9,900
Nancy Foster Rochester, NY	To conduct one workshop at St. John Fisher College in support of the IMLS funded project "New Communities of Knowledge"	1/23/2012	\$3,300
Nancy Foster Rochester, NY	To conduct one Undergraduate Research Behavior Workshop at Westminster College in Salt Lake City, UT on September 13-14, 2011	7/7/2011	\$3,300
Fray Angélico Chávez History Library (Museum of New Mexico Foundation) Santa Fe, NM	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Mapas históricos de Nuevo México = Historic New Mexico Maps"	12/9/2011	\$179,600
Free Library of Philadelphia Philadelphia, PA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Milestones in 20th Century American Children's Literature at the Free Library of Philadelphia"	11/13/2009	\$264,945
Michael Furlough, University Park, PA	To research business planning methods and academic library services that support campus-based publishing and research data management	2/17/2011	\$50,000
George Mason University Fairfax, VA	To support librarian participation in THATCamp 2010-2011 unconferences	6/11/2010	\$5,000
George Mason University Fairfax, VA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering a Forbidden World: Providing Access to East German Art, Culture, and Politics"	11/13/2009	\$76,800
Georgetown University Washington, DC	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Undiscovered Printmakers: Hidden Treasures in Georgetown University's Library"	12/9/2011	\$95,200

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Getty Research Institute Los Angeles, CA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Open Plan, Open Access: Increasing Researcher Access to Modern Architectural Records"	3/14/2011	\$154,579
Hagley Museum and Library Wilmington, DE	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Z. Taylor Vinson Transportation Collection Processing Project"	12/16/2010	\$246,100
Geneva Henry Houston, TX	To conduct research and write a report leading to a prototype proposal for the DPLA Betasprint Challenge	6/30/2011	\$7,500
History San Jose San Jose, CA	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Documenting Technology Innovation: Perham Collection of Early Electronics"	12/9/2011	\$86,600
Intelligent Television New York, NY	To organize panels of professionals from the fields of media, education and technology for the public opening of the Library of Congress's Culpeper campus	7/8/2008	\$45,000
Lori Jahnke and Andrew Asher Philadelphia, PA	To conduct an anthropological study analyzing the institutional environments at five libraries, identifying how the professional culture hinders or supports digital curation efforts	7/26/2011	\$15,000
Lori Jahnke and Amanda Watson Philadelphia, PA	To analyze reports submitted by recipients of CLIR's Mellon Fellowship program for Dissertation Research in Original Sources	5/10/2011	\$15,000
Ryan Kshanipour Flagstaff, AZ	To serve as coordinator for CLIR's 2011 Mellon Fellows Synchronous Sessions	10/26/2011	\$1,000
Todd Krater Lakemoor, IL	To provide services related to ongoing maintenance of our online application systems	9/3/2009	\$5,150
Lehigh University Bethlehem, PA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The Moravian Community in the New World: The First 100 Years"	11/13/2009	\$90,552
Library of Congress Washington, DC	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Library of Congress Multi-Sheet Map Series Collection: Africa"	12/1/2008	\$240,240
Maine Maritime Museum Bath, ME	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Merchant Mariners Muster: Cataloging Crew Manuscripts"	12/9/2011	\$125,600.00
McMaster University Hamilton, Ontario	To support the hiring, mentorship, and employment of one Data Curation Postdoctoral Fellow	4/11/2012	\$77,400
Media Mechanics San Francisco, CA	To produce a series of four radio programs for the National Recording Registry	11/20/2011	\$8,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Mennonite Historians of Eastern Pennsylvania, Inc. Harleysville, PA	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The Pennsylvania German Textiles of the Goshenhoppen Historians, the Mennonite Heritage Center and the Schwenkfelder Library & Heritage Center"	12/9/2011	\$98,500
Kelly Miller, Michelle Morton and Patricia Hswe Charlottesville, VA	To organize and manage the project, "Observations on Engagement with Hidden Special Collections and Archives"	4/1/2010	\$64,150
Newberry Library Chicago, IL	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "French Pamphlet Collections at the Newberry Library"	11/13/2009	\$488,179
New York Archival Society New York, NY	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Cataloging Artifacts and Related Records of the World Trade Center Attack on September 11, 2001"	12/9/2011	\$120,000
New-York Historical Society New York, NY	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The New-York Historical Society American Almanac Collection"	12/9/2011	\$255,700
New York University New York, NY	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Records of the Communist Party, USA and Library of Reference Center for Marxist Studies"	12/1/2008	\$492,901
North Carolina State University Libraries Raleigh, NC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Changing the Landscape: Exposing the legacy of Modernist Architects and Landscape Architects"	11/13/2009	\$221,023
North Carolina State University Libraries Raleigh, NC	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Acting for Animals: Revealing the Records of Animal Rights and Animal Welfare Movements"	12/9/2011	\$219,600
Northeast Historic Film Bucksport, ME	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Moving Images 1938-1940: Amateur Filmmakers Record the New York World's Fair and Its Period"	12/16/2010	\$186,900
Jerry Persons San Mateo, CA	To conduct an in-depth survey of current publications, programs, tools which generate or make use of Semantic Web, Linked Data, and RDF Triples Technologies	3/24/2011	\$40,000
Regents of the University of California Berkeley, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project San Francisco Examiner Photograph Archive Project	11/13/2009	\$306,446
Regents of the University of California Berkeley, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "University and Jepson Herbaria"	12/1/2008	\$253,794
Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey Newark, NJ	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Cataloging Women in Jazz Collections at the Institute of Jazz Studies"	12/9/2011	\$165,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
San Diego Historical Society San Diego, CA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Enhancing Access to the History of San Diego and the Border Region"	12/16/2010	\$162,100
San Diego Museum of Man San Diego, CA	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Capturing History: Cataloging the San Diego Museum of Man's Photographic Collection"	12/9/2011	\$115,200
Dawn Schmitz and Michelle Morton Greensboro, NC	To conduct background research on humanities funding	1/17/2012	\$2,400
Smithsonian Institution Washington, DC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project Exposing Biodiversity Fieldbooks and Original Expedition Journals at the Smithsonian Institution	11/13/2009	\$498,239
Smithsonian Institution, Archives of American Art Washington, DC	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering Hidden Audio Visual Media Documenting Post-Modern Art at the Archives of American Art"	12/9/2011	\$222,700
Smithsonian Institution/Freer Gallery of Art and Sackler Gallery Washington, D.C.	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Islamic Arts of the Book at the Smithsonian: Providing for Research Across Disciplines"	12/16/2011	\$82,500
Stanford University Stanford, CA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Documenting Mexican American and Latino Civil Rights"	12/16/2010	\$349,300
Maureen Sullivan Annapolis, MD	To develop a work restructuring workshop to support the IMLS funded project, "Leadership through New Communities of Knowledge"	2/4/2011	\$6,000
Syracuse University Syracuse, NY	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Grove Press and a New American Morality"	12/16/2010	\$143,100
Texas A&M University College Station, TX	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Discovering a New World: Cataloging Old and Rare Imprints from Colonial and Early Independent Mexico"	12/9/2011	\$84,500
Ann Thornton Annapolis, MD	To assist CLIR with the final stages of content migration for the new website	12/6/2011	\$2,000
University of California, Berkeley Berkeley, CA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Cataloging Hidden Archives of the University of California Museum of Paleontology"	12/16/2010	\$236,200
University of California, Berkeley Museum of Vertebrate Zoology Berkeley, CA	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Cataloging Hidden Archives of the Museum of Vertebrate Zoology: Increasing Integration and Accessibility for Interdisciplinary Research"	12/9/2011	\$481,800
University of California, Santa Barbara University Art Museum Santa Barbara, CA	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Cataloging Southern California's architectural history"	12/9/2011	\$183,500

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
University of Chicago Chicago, IL	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The 'Color Curtain' Processing Project: Unveiling the University of Chicago's Black Metropolis"	12/16/2010	\$499,408
University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign, Champaign, IL	To support work for the project entitled "Developing a Prototype for the Digital Public Library of America"	9/12/2011	\$20,564
University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign, Champaign, IL	To provide basic maintenance for 169 collections held within the DLF American History Online collections in the IMLS DCC repository	4/15/2011	\$12,000
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, MI	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Collaboration in Cataloging: Islamic Manuscripts at Michigan"	12/1/2008	\$225,931
University of Nebraska-Lincoln Libraries Lincoln, NE	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Major Railroad Archival Collections"	12/16/2010	\$208,500
University of North Carolina Chapel Hill Chapel Hill, NC	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The Pruitt and Shanks Photographic Collection"	12/16/2010	\$78,400
University of North Texas Denton, TX	To fund a postdoctoral Student to conduct research in connection with data curation	3/16/2011	\$28,350
University of Pennsylvania Philadelphia, PA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Promoting Research Through Rare Book Cataloging Partnerships"	12/16/2010	\$490,700
University of Pennsylvania Philadelphia, PA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Hidden Collections in the Philadelphia Area: A Consortial Processing and Cataloging Initiative"	12/16/2008	\$500,000
University of Rochester River Campus Rochester, NY	To lead four Faculty and Student Research Behavior Workshops in the calendar year 2011	12/12/2010	\$13,200
University of Southern California Libraries Los Angeles, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Excavating L.A.: USC's Hidden Southern California Historical Collections"	11/13/2009	\$160,000
University of Texas at Austin Austin, TX	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Revealing Texas Collections of Comedias Seltas"	12/16/2010	\$137,100
University of Wisconsin at Milwaukee, American Geographical Society Library Milwaukee, WI	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Providing Access to the Archives of the American Geographical Society"	12/9/2011	\$259,900
Elizabeth Waraksa Los Angeles, CA	To complete a strategic plan document for the IMLS funded project "Co-Plan for Humanities Scholarship"	3/15/2011	\$21,000
WGBH Educational Foundation Boston, MA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Exposing Unknown Boston Local TV News Collections"	12/16/2010	\$311,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Yale Peabody Museum of Natural History New Haven, CT	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "From DNA to Dinosaurs"	12/16/2010	\$409,300
Yale University New Haven, CT	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Song, Speech, and Dance: Special Collections from the Recorded Sound Archives at Yale and Stanford Universities"	11/13/2009	\$457,776

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

**FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

**FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2012
WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT**

**STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia**

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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STONE AND SPRING
CERTIFIED PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS
A Partnership of Professional Corporations

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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
Stephen C. Stone, C.P.A.

INDEPENDENT AUDITOR'S REPORT

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, DC

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources (a nonprofit organization) as of June 30, 2012, and the related statement of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council on Library and Information Resources' management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2012, and the changes in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The schedule of functional expenses on page 33 is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information is the responsibility of management and was derived from and relates directly to the underlying accounting and other records used to prepare the financial statements. The information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and certain additional procedures, including comparing and reconciling such information directly to the underlying accounting and other records used to prepare the financial statements or to the financial statements themselves, and other additional procedures in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. In our opinion, the information is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
August 13, 2012

Members American Institute of Certified Public Accountants

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2012

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporary Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Assets:			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 114,476	\$ 2,529,665	\$ 2,644,141
Investments	99,098	765,219	864,317
Accounts receivable	42,750	397,447	440,197
Furniture and equipment, net	24,140	-	24,140
Other assets	77,046	-	77,046
Total Assets	<u>\$ 357,510</u>	<u>\$ 3,692,331</u>	<u>\$ 4,049,841</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets			
Accounts payable	\$ 187,932	\$ -	\$ 187,932
Capital lease	5,022	-	5,022
Accrued expenses	48,273	-	48,273
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 241,227</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 241,227</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 116,283</u>	<u>\$ 3,692,331</u>	<u>\$ 3,808,614</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u><u>\$ 357,510</u></u>	<u><u>\$ 3,692,331</u></u>	<u><u>\$ 4,049,841</u></u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2012

	Unrestricted	Temporary Restricted	Total
Revenue			
Grants and contracts	\$ -	\$ 3,240,999	\$ 3,240,999
Contributions	790,075	11,205	801,280
Publication sales	1,912	-	1,912
Investment income/(loss)	(2,084)	23,696	21,612
Other income	351,539	13,331	364,870
	<u>\$ 1,141,442</u>	<u>\$ 3,289,231</u>	<u>\$ 4,430,673</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions			
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 2,577,203</u>	<u>\$ (2,577,203)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 3,718,645</u>	<u>\$ 712,028</u>	<u>\$ 4,430,673</u>
Expenses			
Program services:			
Preservation and access	\$ 102,091	\$ -	\$ 102,091
Digital infrastructure	766,089	-	766,089
Leadership, education and cultivation	251,308	-	251,308
Other strategic initiatives	142,303	-	142,303
Communications and publications	45,885	-	45,885
Outreach and collaboration	116,156	-	116,156
Scholarship and research	1,743,777	-	1,743,777
Total Program Services	<u>\$ 3,167,609</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 3,167,609</u>
Administration	<u>670,941</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>670,941</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 3,838,550</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 3,838,550</u>
Change in Net Assets	<u>\$ (119,905)</u>	<u>\$ 712,028</u>	<u>\$ 592,123</u>
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	\$ 236,188	\$ 2,980,303	\$ 3,216,491
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 116,283</u>	<u>\$ 3,692,331</u>	<u>\$ 3,808,614</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the year ended June 30, 2012

Operating Activities	
Change in net assets	\$ 592,123
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) operating activities:	
Depreciation	13,163
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	3,387
(Increase) decrease in other assets	22,901
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	(373,209)
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	83,571
	<hr/>
Net Cash Provided (used) by Operating Activities	\$ 341,936
Investing Activities	
Purchases of investments	\$ (766,667)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	(9,640)
	<hr/>
Net Cash Provided (Used) by Investing Activities	\$ (776,307)
Financing Activities	
Principal payments on capital lease	\$ (1,944)
	<hr/>
Net Cash Provided (Used) by Financing Activities	\$ (1,944)
Net Change in Cash and Cash equivalents	\$ (436,315)
Cash and Cash Equivalents, Beginning of Year	\$ 3,080,456
Cash and Cash Equivalents, End of Year	\$ 2,644,141
	<hr/> <hr/>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information:	
Interest paid during the year	\$ -
	<hr/> <hr/>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2012

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council on Library and Information Resources is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council on Library and Information Resources operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council on Library and Information Resources conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council on Library and Information Resources reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council on Library and Information Resources are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs - Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent grant receivable, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council on Library and Information Resources management has evaluated accounts receivable collection from prior years and has determined that an allowance for doubtful accounts is not necessary.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2012
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council on Library and Information Resources records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2012 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

Subsequent Events- In preparing these financial statements, The Council on Library and Information Resources has evaluated events and transactions for potential recognition or disclosure through the date the financial statements were issued

NOTE 3- Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

Furniture and equipment	\$ 98,440
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(74,300)</u>
	<u>\$ 24,140</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2012
(Continued)

NOTE 4- Investments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has adopted SFAS No. 124, "Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations." Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2012

	<u>Gain/(loss) on Investments</u>	<u>Unrealized Gain/(loss) on Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ -	\$ -	-
Bonds	-	-	-
Corporate fixed income	-	-	-
Government securities	-	-	-
Certificates of deposit	-	-	-
Mutual funds	-	(3,387)	864,317
Subtotal	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ (3,387)</u>	<u>\$ 864,317</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	-	-	\$ 2,644,141
Total	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ (3,387)</u>	

The following schedule summarizes the investment and cash equivalent return and its classification in the statement of activities for the year ended June 30, 2012:

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Interest and dividends	\$ 1,303	\$ 23,696	\$ 24,999
Realized gains (losses)	-	-	-
Unrealized gains (losses)	(3,387)	-	(3,387)
Total investment return	<u>\$ (2,084)</u>	<u>\$ 23,696</u>	<u>\$ 21,612</u>

NOTE 5 - Income Taxes

The Council on Library and Information Resources is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2012
(Continued)

NOTE 6 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 7 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council on Library and Information Resources defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council on Library and Information Resources contributions. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributions were \$132,322 in 2012.

NOTE 8 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council on Library and Information Resources to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2012, the Council on Library and Information Resources held \$864,317 in investments. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank included in noninterest bearing accounts at June 30, 2012 is fully insured under FDIC. Uninsured amounts that are interest bearing are insured up to \$250,000. At June 30, 2012, the uninsured cash balance was \$2,249,285. In 2010, the FDIC started a program called the Dodd-Frank provision that provides unlimited coverage on deposits for noninterest bearing account holders. The program ends December 31, 2012.

The Council on Library and Information Resources received \$1,458,000 and \$672,697 from two organizations which represents 33 % and 15% of total revenue respectively.

NOTE 9 - Accounts Receivable

	June 30, <u>2012</u>
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 425,898
30 - 60 days	14,299
60 - 90 days	-
Over 90 days	-
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u>-</u>
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>\$ 440,197</u>

NOTE 10 - Commitments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into two noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August , 2018 and April , 2019 . The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into a sublease with another organization that it collects rent from which expires August , 2018. Rental expense, for the year ending June 30, 2012 was \$268,134. The Council on Library and Information Resources is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in January 2015.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2012
(Continued)

NOTE 10 - Commitments (continued)

Future minimum lease payments under all leases net of amounts collected from subtenant with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending <u>June 30,</u>	Capital <u>Lease</u>	Operating <u>Leases</u>	Subtenant <u>Lease</u>	Net Operating <u>Leases</u>
2013	\$ 1,944	\$ 380,837	\$ (216,384)	\$ 164,453
2014	1,944	393,140	(244,190)	148,950
2015	1,134	405,832	(252,736)	153,096
2016	-	418,944	(261,582)	157,362
2017	-	432,489	(270,738)	161,751
2018 and beyond	-	602,259	(328,270)	273,989
Total minimum lease payments	\$ 5,022	<u>\$2,633, 501</u>	<u>\$ (1,573,900)</u>	<u>\$1,059,601</u>
Less: Amount representing interest.	_____	-		
Present value of net minimum lease payments		<u>\$ 5,022</u>		

NOTE 11- Board Designated Net Assets Funds

The Board of Directors voted to designate net assets of \$400,000 for operating reserves.

NOTE 12 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments

The carrying amounts reflected in the balance sheets for cash, cash equivalents, loans and notes payable approximate the respective fair values due to the short maturities of those instruments. SFAS 157 requires a fair value hierarchy to be used to prioritize valuation inputs into three levels:

Level 1 – Quoted prices (unadjusted) in active markets for identical assets or liabilities.

Level 2 – Observable inputs other than the quoted prices included in Level 1.

Level 3 – Unobservable inputs.

Fair values of assets and liabilities measured on a nonrecurring basis at June 30, 2011 are as follows:

Description	Fair Value	(Level 1)	(Level 2)	(Level 3)	(Losses)
Long-lived assets held for sale	\$ 864,317	—	\$ 864,317	\$ -	-

Long-lived assets have been valued using a market approach. The values were determined using market prices of similar long-lived assets.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
For The Year Ended June 30, 2012

	Digital Infrastructure	Outreach and Collaboration	Leadership, Education, and Cultivation	Preservation and Access	Other Strategic Initiatives	Scholarship and Research	Communications and Publications	Total Program	Administration	Total
Employee costs	\$ 307,672	\$ 5,708	\$ 113,652	\$ 86,704	\$ 38,625	\$ 639,071	\$ -	\$ 1,191,432	\$ 131,787	\$ 1,323,219
Professional Services and contracts	72,914	-	15,000	8,000	4,641	78,863	6,141	185,559	213,933	399,492
Fellowships, scholarships and interns	5,775	-	45,685	-	-	551,667	-	603,127	-	603,127
Communications	24,607	94	416	224	8,631	20,733	35,498	90,203	13,303	95,278
Travel and meetings	308,226	102,850	71,531	1,948	85,252	343,414	-	913,221	65,331	978,552
Publications	3,725	-	-	893	1,144	2,384	4,246	12,392	-	12,392
Office operations	23,977	1,333	5,024	2,573	4,010	64,001	-	100,918	317,344	418,262
Indirect	19,193	6,171	-	1,749	-	43,644	-	70,757	(70,757)	-
Total	\$ 766,089	\$ 116,156	\$ 251,308	\$ 102,091	\$ 142,303	\$ 1,743,777	\$ 45,885	\$ 3,167,609	\$ 670,941	\$ 3,838,550

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

